

Effects of Thyroid and Pituitary Hormones Combined Doses and Ponderal Index (Kn) Relationship on Post-embryonic Development in *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.)

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Abstract

Newly hatched larvae of Indian major carp (*Cirrhina mrigala* (Ham.) exposed to combined (thyroid and pituitary hormone) and Ponderal Index by immersion for one month exhibited faster post-embryonic development than correlated with growth as against the control experiments and larvae exposed to individual hormones doses. 100+2 mg/lit. dose of combined (thyroid and Pituitary hormone) proved suitable in all respect. Mortality figure comes out 4, 6, 5 and 10 for 0+0mg/lit., 75+1mg/lit., 100+2mg/lit. and 125+3mg/lit. dose treatment respectively. The study revealed that there was a close relationship between growth and development. There is a very important aspect of morphometrical parameters showed marked changes in all combined (thyroid and Pituitary hormone) treated experiment (Cultural investigation). These observations suggest that most powerful hormone therapy may have prove in the practical utility in the hatchery reared culture of freshwater Indian major carps, *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.).

Keywords

Thyroid hormone, Pituitary hormone, post-embryonic development, Ponderal Index (Kn), *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.)

Introduction

The thyroid and pituitary hormone have been known as the most important biochemical substances, which are responsible for metamorphic differentiation during larval development period along with many physiological process of prime importance (Belsare et. al;1966).

The maintenance of adequate balance of thyroid and pituitary hormone levels are important prerequisite for proper management of reproductive biology, development, growth and its may prove important regulating factor. The effect of thyroxine hormone treatment along with the pituitary in a combined form on post-embryonic development of *Cirrhina mrigala* is not yet fully known and needs further investigation. With this view point in the present communication, an effort has been made to work out the optimum combined dose of thyroid and pituitary hormones which could be able to affect some aspects of post-embryonic development in a positive direction.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study the effects of thyroid and pituitary hormones combined doses and Ponderal Index (Kn) relationship on post-embryonic Development in *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.).

Review of Literature

Some of the important studies on the said field are from Hoar et. al.(1955); Lostroh et. al. (1958); Scow (1959); Sneed et. al. (1961); Nicall et. al. (1965); Belsare et. al. (1966); Yamazaki (1976); Holder et. al. (1980); Miwa et. al. (1985); Tay et. al. (1997); Lakra , et.al. (1996); Wilson ,et al.(1998); Islam, et. al.(2021); Hasan, et.al. (2021); Romain ,et.al. (2022). Brown et.al.(1995) and that of Nayak et. al. (2000).

Methodology

The hatchlings (3-4 days old) of *Cirrhina mrigala* (Ham.) were collected from fish farm in the close vicinity of Raebareli. The hatchlings for consecutive development stages were brought to laboratory and transferred to plastic trough under observation. In each experimental trough, 20 specimens were placed on the basis of proper stocking density (Approximately 2 fish /lit.). The physico-chemical conditions of the experimental troughs were maintained merely natural by the use of sand particles, hydrilla plant, zoo and phytoplanktons. Hitachi readymade food pellets in quantity were also given at regular intervals to all the experimental larvae. The combined (thyroid and pituitary hormone) doses of 75+1mg/lit., 100+2mg/lit. and 125+3mg/lit concentration were prepared by pituitary extract alcoholic method from the common carp and in each trough one kind of them was added.

By random sampling five specimens from each kind of experiment and control were taken out for derivation of mean standard under different aspects of studies on post-embryonic development at a successive time period 30 days in order to study later developmental stages. Morphometrical parameters of the larvae were recorded with the help of Venier Calipers and weighing balance machine at the end of the experiments.

Ponderal Index (length weight relationship) on the post embryonic development and growth was calculated on the basis of the following equation:-

$$K_n = \frac{W \times 10^5}{L^3}$$

Where, K_n = Ponderal Index

W = weight of fish

L = Length of fish

10^5 = Bringing the Ponderal Index (K_n) near the unit (Carlander, 1970)

Result and Discussion

On the perusal of the parameters indicated in the Table 1, it can be concluded that a dose 100+2mg/lit. proved to be the best in term of post-embryonic development (Fig. 1, 2 & Table 1).

Table 1: Morphometry of *Cirrhina mrigala* (Ham.) larvae treated with combined doses of thyroid (T) and pituitary (P) hormone (mg/lit.).

S.No.	General Measurement	000mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	75+1mg/lit.(T1+P1) (Average in mean \pm S.D)	100+2mg/lit.(T2+P2) (Average in mean \pm S.D)	125+3mg/lit (T3+P3). (Average in mean \pm S.D)
1	Standard Length	21.897 \pm 0.048	33.247 \pm 1.564	37.535 \pm 1.533	37.067 \pm 1.337
2	Body Length	13.397 \pm 0.010	22.242 \pm 0.892	25.295 \pm 1.652	25.660 \pm 0.843
3	Head Length	06.307 \pm 0.036	08.322 \pm 0.867	09.562 \pm 0.907	08.55 \pm 1.843
4	Distance Between snout and anal pore	14.892 \pm 0.061	21.987 \pm 1.793	26.170 \pm 1.580	23.685 \pm 0.963
5	Distance Between snout and anal fin base	16.677 \pm 0.090	26.382 \pm 3.176	29.025 \pm 0.883	29.460 \pm 0.812
6	Distance Between snout and dorsal fin base	13.552 \pm 0.068	21.332 \pm 0.996	22.852 \pm 1.317	22.705 \pm 0.811
7	Height of the body at anal fin base	04.887 \pm 0.109	07.222 \pm 0.925	07.617 \pm 1.091	07.522 \pm 0.659
8	Height of the body at dorsal fin base	06.747 \pm 0.074	09.405 \pm 0.965	09.690 \pm 0.818	08.240 \pm 1.305
9	Body Weight	88.876 \pm 0.486	118.068 \pm 0.363	120.126 \pm 0.244	119.962 \pm 0.128
10	Ponderal Index	0.846	0.321	0.227	0.235
11	Mortality	Four	six	five	Ten

The general morphometrical parameters of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham) larvae revealed that a dose of 100+2mg/lit., standard length 37.535mm; body length 25.295mm; head length 9.562mm; distance between snout and anal pore 26.170mm; distance between snout and anal fin base 29.025mm; distance between a snout and dorsal fin base 22.852mm; height of the body at anal fin base 7.617mm; height of the body at dorsal fin base 9.690mm; and body weight 120.126mg was observed, which is significant in terms of the best estimated in correspondence to post-embryonic development.

It has also been marked those early developmental periods when morphogenesis is on its full swing, the combined thyroid and pituitary hormone treatment resulted into maximum increment in standard body length at 100+2mg/lit. dose. Survival percentage was maximum in control which gradually decreased at 75+1mg/lit; 100+2mg/lit. and 125+3mg/lit. dose treatment (Table1)

The application of T2P2 (100+2mg/Lit.) for 30 days duration of the experiment prove to be the best in term of total length in comparison to control and other combined thyroid and pituitary hormone doses.

Ponderal Index is calculated for different doses of combined thyroid and pituitary hormone in treatment of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for 30 days experiment. As Fig. 2 the ponderal index showed decrement in respect to control sets. The best result in terms of

minimum ponderal index at T2 P2(100+2mg/lit.) provide the values as 0.227 for 30 days experiment.

Conclusion

Therefore, 100+2mg/lit. dose was calculated to be the best effective dose in respect to post-embryonic development and low mortality of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) larvae.

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